

Now, according to this mechanism, the corresponding salt of the acid (III in the above equation) on degassing at high temperatures should evolve the same amount of carbon dioxide as the original charcoal, while, if it is formed according to the mechanism represented by equation 2, it should evolve more carbon dioxide than the original charcoal, as shown below :

the metallic oxide reacting at the prevailing high temperature with carbon to produce an equivalent amount of carbon dioxide in addition.

This point can be verified by evacuating charcoal before and after replacing surface H^+ ions with different amounts of different metal cations.

The work described in this paper was undertaken with these objectives in view.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal, prepared by carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar with H_2SO_4 (conc.), followed by exhaustive washings with water, was used. Its base-adsorption capacity (b.a.c.), as determined by shaking 1 g. with 100 c.c. of 0.2N-Ba(OH)₂ solution for about 24 hours in the usual way, was found to be 674.8 m.e. per 100 g. The H-charcoal was then converted into Li^+ , Na^+ , Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} charcoals by shaking 10 g. portions with increasing amounts of 0.2N solutions of the corresponding alkalis (using solid CaO and MgO for preparing Ca- and Mg-charcoals). The amounts of alkalis added were well within the base-neutralising capacity of the charcoal. The suspensions were refluxed for about 8 to 10 hours, followed by shaking for 48 hours. The clear supernatant liquid was decanted off and the charcoal was washed repeatedly with CO_2 -free distilled water to remove unchanged alkali, if any. The amounts of the various cations introduced into the charcoal complex were determined by shaking 1 g. samples (oven-dried at 110°) with 100 c.c. of 0.1N-HCl for about 24 hours and estimating the amount of lithium chloride and sodium chloride brought into solution by evaporating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid to dryness, and those of magnesium, calcium and barium by the usual gravimetric procedures.

A sample of charcoal was also activated in steam at 1000° under optimum conditions (Singh *et al.*, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, 21, 187).

Water Isotherms and Surface Area.—Water vapour adsorption isotherms were determined at 25° by the procedure described before (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 841). Surface areas were calculated from the isotherms by the method suggested by Harvey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2343).

Heats of Immersion.—Charcoal samples (2-4 g.) were taken into thin-walled glass bulbs and outgassed for about 2 hours at the room temperature. The heat of immersion was determined by breaking these bulbs in excess (300 c.c.) of water by following the technique described by Boyd and Harkins (*ibid.*, 1942, 64, 1190).

Evacuation at 1200°.—The various samples of charcoal (2 g. portions) were subjected to evacuation at 1200° in a resistance-tube furnace and the gases evolved were analysed in an Orsat-Lunge gas-analysis apparatus in the usual manner.

TABLE I

Effect of replacing H⁺ ions by different amounts of different metal cations on water isotherms and surface areas of sugar charcoal.

Amount of metal cations introduced in exchange for H ⁺ ion (m.e./100 g.).	Amount of water vapour adsorbed (g./100 g.) at relative vapour pressure.						Surface area (m. ² /g.)
	0.10.	0.30.	0.50.	0.70.	0.90.	0.99.	
0.00 (H-charcoal)	2.61	5.26	9.73	12.21	18.70	27.55	421.0
Li⁺-charcoal							
121.0	5.58	7.12	10.58	13.01	26.34	40.50	401.2
157.3	7.24	9.44	12.86	18.79	29.48	47.32	426.5
229.9	8.62	12.50	16.74	22.58	37.81	66.64	400.1
266.2	9.91	12.68	18.81	24.02	40.12	72.66	440.2
438.8	11.03	14.37	20.01	26.09	45.90	80.56	430.8
Na-charcoal							
96.8	5.20	7.21	10.19	13.53	25.76	40.20	400.4
114.4	7.12	9.49	11.26	17.50	28.04	61.00	398.4
198.1	8.32	9.81	12.04	17.84	29.79	65.33	409.1
220.0	9.01	10.25	16.74	21.70	35.72	70.18	416.5
448.9	10.98	12.39	17.01	22.68	36.94	76.89	406.8
Mg-charcoal							
135.8	4.41	7.25	10.62	11.78	19.95	28.11	416.8
232.5	6.36	9.01	11.42	12.59	21.90	32.04	441.2
409.0	9.30	11.42	14.10	17.56	27.62	37.82	399.2
Ca-charcoal							
145.2	4.01	6.75	10.14	14.16	20.32	29.20	399.7
169.4	5.10	7.56	11.41	14.59	21.10	30.24	405.6
411.4	7.51	9.42	12.21	15.82	25.24	36.24	433.9
Ba-charcoal							
133.0	4.00	5.61	9.79	12.51	18.76	29.50	426.2
217.8	4.71	7.02	10.82	13.62	20.06	30.15	410.8
425.6	7.10	9.82	13.22	16.23	23.56	33.58	430.8
Steam-activated charcoal	3.72	13.95	15.72	28.91	36.36	45.27	...

DISCUSSION

From Table I it appears that the moisture-adsorption values increase at all relative vapour pressures on the replacement of H⁺ ions by increasing amounts of different metal cations, and that the effect is more in case of monovalent than in the case

of bivalent cations. The replacement of H^+ ions to the extent of about 440 m.e./100 g. (out of total base-exchange capacity of 675 m.e./100 g. of the charcoal) for instance, causes two-fold to three-fold increase in the moisture-adsorption capacity of the charcoal from the atmospheres of different relative humidities. It is also interesting to note that the adsorption values, obtained on the introduction of Li^+ or Na^+ , are even higher than those obtained on activating the charcoal in steam at 1000° under optimum conditions. This shows that the introduction of alkali cations makes the charcoal surface extremely hydr ophilic. At the same time this places at our disposal a very convenient method for preparing an efficient water-adsorbent charcoal.

Since the surface area of charcoal undergoes little or no change on the replacement of H^+ ions by different metal cations (Table I, last column), the increase in moisture-adsorption capacity of charcoal cannot be attributed to this factor. The increase is probably due to the greater surface ionisation of charcoal with metal cations than that of H-charcoal on analogy with greater dissociation of alkali salts of weak acids than that of the acids themselves.

FIG. 1

The comparative effect of the various metal cations is brought out clearly in Fig. 1, in which the isotherms of charcoal containing nearly the same amounts of different cations have been plotted. It is evident that lithium produces maximum increase, followed closely by sodium. Magnesium-, calcium- and barium-charcoals afford lower values probably due to smaller ionisation on analogy with the salts of these bases. The difference may also be partly due to a smaller degree of hydration of these ions. It is interesting to note in this connection that the effect of the various cations decreases in about the same order as their degree of hydration.

The replacement of H^+ ions by other cations also causes an appreciable increase in the heat of immersion of charcoal in water (Table II), the increase, for a given cation, being in proportion to its amount, as is evident from the values recorded in the last column of Table II. The effect per m.e. is maximum in the case of lithium, followed closely by sodium, and is minimum in the case of magnesium and barium, which provide almost identical values. These results are in accord with those obtained for the moisture adsorption, recorded in Table I.

TABLE II

Heat of immersion of different samples of charcoal in water:

Amount of metal cations introduced in exchange for H^+ ions.	Heat of immersion.	Increase in heat per m.e. of the cation introduced.	Amount of metal cations introduced in exchange for H^+ ions.	Heat of immersion	Increase in heat per m.e. of the cation introduced.
0.00 (H-charcoal)	1625.3	...	...	...	...
Li charcoal.			Mg-charcoal.		
121.0 m.e./100 g.	2628.7 cal./100 g.	8.26 cal.	135.8 m.e./100 g.	2162.1 cal./100 g.	3.96 Cal.
157.3	2965.5	8.52	232.5	2532.3	3.90
229.9	3579.4	8.50	409.0	3255.5	3.98
266.2	3884.6	8.45	Ca-charcoal		
438.8	5289.2	8.35	145.2	2402.4	5.35
			169.4	2557.3	5.50
			411.4	3847.4	5.41
Na-charcoal.			Ba-charcoal.		
96.8	2306.7	7.05			
114.4	2437.5	7.10	133.0	2130.3	3.80
198.1	3029.9	7.09	217.8	2480.5	3.92
220.0	3196.1	7.14	425.6	3327.3	4.00
448.9	4816.9	7.11			

In order to see if the replacement of surface H^+ ions by the metal cations has produced any permanent change in the surface characteristics, all the samples of sodium charcoal were converted back into H-charcoal by leaching with dilute hydrochloric acid, followed by repeated washings with water. The moisture-adsorption capacity and the heat of wetting in every case were found to be the same as those of the original charcoal. These H-charcoals were then reconverted into sodium charcoals and the values were again found to increase to their previous levels. It is evident therefore that the charcoal surface does not undergo any permanent change; its characteristics at any time depend upon the nature and the amount of the surface cations held by it.

TABLE III

Gases evolved on evacuating different samples of charcoal containing different amounts of different cations at 1200°.

Amount of metal cations introduced in exchange of H ⁺ ions (m.e./100 g.).	Gases evolved (in mg./g.) on evacuation at 1200°.				Increase in CO ₂ evolved (mg./g.).	Increase in CO ₂ expected theoretically (mg./g.).
	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ O.	H ₂ .		
0.0 (H-charcoal)	148.46	120.63	125.50	13.51	—	—
Li-charcoal						
121.0	177.88	119.89	126.65	13.50	29.42	26.62
157.3	182.27	120.79	124.98	13.51	33.81	34.61
220.9	207.03	121.05	125.50	12.95	52.62	50.58
265.2	208.51	120.81	125.50	12.90	60.05	58.36
438.8	244.15	120.50	124.80	13.15	95.70	96.54
Na-charcoal						
66.8	171.31	121.05	126.58	13.51	22.85	22.30
114.4	173.36	121.00	126.00	13.49	24.90	25.17
198.1	194.01	120.63	125.90	13.40	45.55	43.58
220.0	198.47	120.10	125.55	13.55	50.01	48.40
448.0	248.40	121.68	126.90	13.57	99.34	98.76
Mg-charcoal						
135.8	177.51	119.89	124.95	12.60	29.05	29.82
232.5	202.39	120.63	125.80	13.69	53.93	52.15
409.0	238.61	120.60	125.50	12.85	90.15	89.96
Ca-charcoal						
145.2	180.95	121.69	125.95	13.50	32.49	31.94
169.4	185.43	121.05	124.99	13.55	36.97	37.27
412.4	241.36	121.15	125.50	13.69	92.90	90.52
Ba-charcoal						
133.0	178.61	120.69	126.01	13.51	30.15	29.26
217.8	198.46	121.00	125.59	13.99	50.00	47.92
425.6	243.27	120.89	125.91	13.55	91.81	93.63

The results of analysis of the gases, evolved from the various samples of charcoal on evacuation at 1200°, are recorded in Table III. It is seen that there is little or no change in the amounts of CO, H₂O and H₂ evolved on the introduction of different cations. However, an appreciable increase in the amount of CO₂ is noticed. This indicates that the mechanism of base adsorption, as postulated by Garten and Weiss (*loc. cit.*), may not be quite correct. It appears more likely that the mechanism proposed by Puri *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), as represented by equation (2), is nearer the truth. This view receives further support from the fact that the increase in the value of CO₂ evolved, as calculated from the amounts of the cations held by the charcoal, is

accordance with equation (4), is quite close to the increase actually observed in every case with the exception of magnesium charcoal, where the increase actually observed is less than that expected theoretically. This discrepancy is understandable since it is well known that magnesium oxide does not part with its oxygen readily even at high temperatures.

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